

FEATURES OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM IN PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM CHRONIC INSOMNIA AND PROSPECTS FOR IDENTIFYING SOMATIC SLEEP DISORDERS

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Аннотация: The prevalence of various forms of insomnia among the working population requires an individual approach to prevention based on understanding the main pathophysiological factors that lead to sleep disorders and associated somatic problems. This prevents the risks of sleep disorders and their negative impact on overall health. **Objective:** To study the state of brain function and cerebral circulation in specialists engaged in mental work, exposed to high levels of stress and sleep problems, and to identify risk factors contributing to the occurrence of these disorders, in order to scientifically substantiate preventive measures. **Object of the study:** Two groups of patients were studied - mental workers with a high level of professional stress (class 3.3) and work stress. The main group included 77 people who reported insomnia (insomnia severity index was 20.4 ± 3.1 points); the control group included 88 people without significant sleep disorders. A clinical and instrumental study was conducted, covering a questionnaire, a night polysomnographic study, as well as electroencephalographic (EEG) and rheographic studies. **Results:** Workers with sleep disorders had a high level of work-related stress, which statistically correlated with a deterioration in total sleep time, a decrease in the proportion of slow-wave sleep and an increase in the fragmentation of night rest, which was manifested in an increase in activation reactions on the EEG ($r = 0.35$). The study of cerebral blood flow showed that 50% of participants with sleep disorders and 32% without them had instability of vascular tone. Prospective observation data indicated that 92% of patients with nonspecific EEG changes, which were characterized by a predominance of low-amplitude high-frequency activity, retained signs of sleep disorders, while similar signs were observed in 65% of patients without these changes.

Key words: Chronic sleep disorders; insomnia; stress at work; functional aspects of the central nervous system; polysomnography; electroencephalography; rheography of cerebral vessels; measures for the prevention of sleep disorders.

Introduction

Chronic sleep onset and sleep maintenance disorders, known as insomnia, are a common problem among working-age workers and have a negative impact on their health, emotional state, and quality of life. The International Classification of Sleep Disorders defines insomnia as the presence of difficulty initiating or maintaining sleep, which is accompanied by daytime consequences and is not caused by unfavorable environmental conditions or lack of opportunities for rest. There are more than 20 types of sleep disorders, the main manifestation of which is insomnia. This disorder is considered chronic if it occurs at least three times a week for at least three months. A wide range of clinical conditions associated with sleep disorders

justifies the need for an individual approach to diagnosis and therapy, taking into account pathophysiological mechanisms. Issues related to the mechanisms of development of various forms of chronic insomnia and their relationship with work stress require further study. The aim of this study is to assess the functional state of the brain and blood flow in knowledge workers with high levels of stress and insomnia, as well as to identify risk factors to justify preventive intervention. In the framework of the study in a multi-specialty hospital, the division into two groups was carried out: experimental and control. The first group consisted of 77 participants suffering from chronic insomnia (including 34 men and 33 women with an average age of 52.8 ± 10.1 years), all of them were engaged in mental work in the sphere of state institutions at the level of stress class 3.3. The second group included 88 people without sleep disorders (comparable by gender and age: 52 men and 36 women, average age - 53.1 ± 10.9 years), also engaged in mental work in similar conditions.

Methodology

Two key models were used for the analysis:

- The demand-control model of work stress,
- The concept of imbalance between efforts and rewards [4,6], which defines a chronic professional stress situation through the discrepancy between high expended efforts and a low level of compensation.

The external effort was assessed using six parameters of workload and job demands. Reward was analyzed using 12 indicators, including the status of the work position, the degree of independence in decision-making and financial aspects.

Internal effort was measured through:

- The need for stimulation,
- Competitive environment among employees,
- Increased level of irritability and intolerance,
- Inability to rest outside of working hours.

The following integral indicators were used for the analysis: the index of imbalance of efforts-reward (a value of > 1 indicates high stress, < 1 - low) and the degree of psychological involvement in work. To diagnose sleep disorders, a clinical examination and questionnaires were used using the Insomnia Severity Scale, where the score varied from 0 to 28 points.

To assess sleep parameters, a comprehensive examination was organized using polysomnography: measurements of four channels of electroencephalograms (EEG), two electrodes for measuring eye and muscle movements, as well as recording cardiographic indicators, respiration by air exchange and respiratory effort taking into account the oxygen saturation of the blood. The data were processed according to the standards of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine.

Psychophysiological diagnostics included frequency analysis of the EEG in two leads both during wakefulness and sleep to assess the state of the central nervous system (CNS). Rheoencephalography, a functional study of cerebral vessels, was performed in both groups. Statistical data processing was performed using the SPSS 12 software package for Windows, where the Student t-test and χ^2 -criterion were used to determine the reliability of differences in mean values and relative values, respectively. Correlation analysis was used to analyze relationships.

Results:

According to the survey using the Insomnia Severity Scale, the average score in the main group of patients suffering from sleep disorders was 20.4 ± 3.1 points, indicating significant sleep problems; in the control group, this index was significantly lower — 5.5 ± 2.1 points.

Polysomnographic data revealed changes in the sleep structure in patients with chronic insomnia: a decrease in the quality and duration of deep slow-wave (3rd) sleep, as well as increased fragmentation of night rest. In the main group, 43% of patients had objectively confirmed disorders with a reduction in total sleep time.

Table 1 shows data on the identified cases of insomnia with a decrease in sleep duration, and Table 2 contains a comparative analysis of the results of polysomnographic research in subgroups of workers by the degree of severity of professional stress. The data obtained indicate that a high level of work stress in workers was associated with a decrease in the total time and efficiency of sleep, a decrease in slow-wave sleep in its structure, and increased fragmentation of sleep due to an increase in EEG activation reactions. A negative correlation was established between sleep efficiency and the effort-reward balance ($r = -0.37$).

Standard EEG tests performed four hours after awakening also showed a higher frequency of non-specific signs of brainstem activation in workers with severe work stress and clinically significant insomnia (55% in the main group and 13% in the control group). In patients with chronic insomnia, non-specific EEG changes were observed - insufficient regularity, weak modulation, periodic disturbances and smoothing of zonal differences in the main (cortical) resting rhythm. These changes were more often observed in the right occipital-parietal lead. Frequent bilateral synchronized and sharpened high-amplitude theta waves were recorded, probably of brainstem origin, which increased during functional testing (hyperventilation and light stimulation for 3 min). Low-amplitude high-frequency irregular beta activity was also detected in the parietal-central-frontal leads, mainly in the left hemisphere. In EEG studies of people without sleep disorders, biopotentials corresponded to age criteria. In the main group, theta region activity was detected significantly more often than in the control group. Rheographic study of cerebral blood flow showed that in 35% of the main group and 14% of the control group, vascular tone changed towards an increase, the wave top flattened, the duration of the ascending wave increased, the descending additional wave moved to the wave top, the severity of the incision scar decreased, pulse blood flow and peripheral vascular resistance decreased. In 50% of subjects with sleep disorders and 32% of subjects without sleep disorders, instability of vascular tone was recorded in the form of constant alternation of normal, hypertensive and hypotensive. Disturbances in venous outflow were observed in the overwhelming majority of subjects. The obtained data may indicate that in individuals

Table 1

Main characteristics of sleep in patients with insomnia and in individuals without sleep disorders (according to polysomnography data)

Sleep structure parameters	Main group, n = 77	Control group, n = 88
Sleep latency, min	34.1±21.1	13.1±10.7*
Total sleep time, min	308.1±72.9	412.5*
Sleep efficiency, %	83.5±8.1	93.5±5.1*
Number of awakenings, events	7.1±4.7	2.2±2.1*
EEG activation reaction index, events per hour	23.1±9.1	12.6±8.1*
% Stage 3 slow wave sleep	7.4±4.2	12.1±5.5
% REM sleep	16.1±5.2	17.3±5.3
Apnea-hypopnea index, %	3.3±2.5	4.6±4.1

Note: Here and in Tables 2 and 3 * - $p < 0.05$.

subject to chronic stress and insomnia, not only local but also central mechanisms of vascular regulation are disrupted. The revealed changes in the functional state of the central nervous system can be considered as a criterion for early diagnostics of an unfavorable course of insomnia. Thus, the results of a questionnaire survey conducted at 13-16 months indicate that among patients who showed insomnia at the beginning of the study, 92% had nonspecific EEG changes with a predominance of low-amplitude high-frequency activity, 65% of patients who did not show such changes had changes in vascular tone according to leioencephalography data of 88% of patients and 68% of those who did not have these changes had persistent signs of sleep disorders.

Table 2

Comparative analysis of polysomnogram parameters in subgroups of workers with different levels of work stress according to the "effort-reward balance" (ERB) indicator

Parameter	Work stress level	
	BUV < 1	BUV ≥ 1
Sleep latency, min	14.1±10.3	20.5±8.3
Total sleep time, min	405.4±61.2	395.2±50.3*
Sleep efficiency, %	93.6±3.1	85.5±9.4*
Activation reaction index, events/h	11.3±7.2	18.6±7.1*
% Stage 3 slow wave sleep	9.1±4.9	4.6±3.2*
% REM sleep	19.5±4.1	19.1±3.9

Discussion

The high prevalence of sleep onset and maintenance disorders (insomnia) among the working-age population and the diversity of clinical manifestations necessitate the development of personalized preventive programs that take into account the key pathophysiological mechanisms that determine the risk of sleep disorders and associated physical diseases. Studies have shown that workers with higher levels of work-related stress and sleep disorders have a more pronounced impairment of the functional state of brain structures, as evidenced by a decrease in the structure of slow-wave sleep and an increase in sleep fragmentation due to increased EEG activation reactions. A positive correlation was noted between the integral indicator of labor intensity and the number of EEG activation reactions ($r = 0.35$) and a negative correlation between sleep efficiency and the effort-reward balance ($r = -$

0.37). Modern concepts of the etiology of chronic insomnia make it possible to identify a fairly large group of patients characterized by excessive activation of the brain stem structures and a certain insufficiency of the "inhibitory" neurophysiological mechanisms. This condition, which has been called "hyperarousal" in the world literature, is also characterized by accelerated metabolism, increased sympathetic activity, and other vegetative changes [7]. Another clinically important change in insomnia is insomnia with an objectively reduced sleep duration [8], which is currently considered an independent risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases. In general, the changes in the functional state of the central and autonomic nervous systems of individuals exposed to increased levels of work stress and/or suffering from sleep disorders, established within the framework of this study, are consistent with modern concepts of the formation of stress-associated disorders and psychosomatic diseases [9, 10].

Conclusion

Based on the data obtained, we can conclude that it is possible to identify a heterogeneous group of patients with complaints of sleep disorders that demonstrate the specificity of the psychological state and physiological changes in the central nervous system, which makes it possible to predict the persistence of sleep disorders in the future.

1. This predisposes to the transition from temporary or transient insomnia to chronic insomnia and, what is especially important, contributes to the development of somatic diseases (mainly cardiovascular) associated with sleep disorders.
2. Sleep disorders (insomnia) and work stress are considered risk factors that contribute to the development of early stages of CNS dysfunction.
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